

Networks and Landscapes: Spatial and Digital Approaches to Medieval Naples and Its Surroundings

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Abstract IT. Il contributo intende analizzare la configurazione territoriale della Napoli medievale (IX – XII secolo) attraverso la documentazione notarile, interpretata come osservatorio privilegiato delle relazioni tra società urbana e territorio. La strutturazione digitale delle attestazioni consente di individuare distribuzioni spaziali, dinamiche cronologiche e livelli di articolazione dei paesaggi agrari documentati. Il caso del monastero di San Sebastiano mostra come le pratiche giuridiche contribuissero alla gestione e alla valorizzazione del territorio.

Keywords: Digital History; Storia Medievale; Mappatura Storica

Abstract EN. This paper analyses the territorial configuration of medieval Naples (9th – 12th centuries) through notarial records, interpreted as a unique vantage point for examining the relationship between urban society and the surrounding territory. The digital structuring of the records makes it possible to identify spatial distributions, chronological dynamics and levels of articulation within the documented agricultural landscapes. The case of the monastery of San Sebastiano shows how juridical practices contributed to the management and development of the territory.

Keywords: Digital History; Medieval History; Spatial and Network Analysis

Introduction

Between the ninth and twelfth centuries, Naples functioned as a highly urbanised centre whose economic and social vitality was deeply intertwined with its surrounding territory, forming an integrated system sustained by the dense circulation of goods, people, rights, and resources [Cuozzo, Martin 1995; Arthur 2002, 83-108; Feniello 2007, 3]. Rather than a simple urban nucleus surrounded by a rural hinterland, the Neapolitan duchy can be defined as an urban-territorial system in which the city and its surrounding areas were linked through economic, social, and juridical relations.

This study approaches notarial documentation as a privileged perspective for observing how this relationship between city and territory was structured in practice. On the one hand, charters constitute one of the most substantial bodies of written documentation preserved for medieval Naples. On the other, they record concrete juridical actions through which lands and properties entered negotiated relationships and became the object of economic and social strategies.

In this sense, the articulation of both rural and urban places became embedded in the ways in which society organised, regulated, and transmitted control over land. The landscapes that appear in the documents – through the description, the transfer and concession of property – acquired relevance within documentary practices and were fixed in juridical form. For this very reason, charters and deeds provide a privileged field of inquiry.

Examining these attestations makes it possible to observe how spatial references take shape within the documentation and how their distribution varies across different parts of the territory and over time. The resulting picture helps reconstruct the space that emerges when land, resources, and productive units become the object of juridical action. Precisely for this reason, the documentary record allows us to identify those areas in which economic activity, rights, and forms of territorial organisation appear most frequently within regulated transactions. Working with a large and fragmentary corpus required transforming charter evidence into a machine-readable dataset – that is, a structure that could be systematically queried. The material was organised to correlate interpretative categories, spatial data, and chronological intervals, allowing patterns of recurrence and variation to be assessed across the documentation.

Digital tools are therefore part of the analytical process itself, combining critical source analysis with data modelling. The aim remains historical: to understand the territorial dynamics of medieval Naples. Digital methods serve to show a dispersed and uneven documentary record can be examined at scale.

1. Documentary *corpus*

The documentary *corpus* on which this study is based was defined through a preliminary survey of the principal collections preserving notarial documentation for medieval Naples. The initial definition of the corpus began during preliminary research conducted for a Master's Thesis [Marcantonio 2024]

and was subsequently expanded and refined for the purposes of the present study. The selection aimed to include acts recording juridical transactions involving lands, properties, and productive resources within the Neapolitan territory. The documentary corpus consists of the *Regii Neapolitani Archivi Monumenta* [Libertini 2011¹] which contains the full transcription of the acts belonging to the first series of the lost archive, published between 1845 and 1861. These are complemented by the *Monumenta ad Neapolitani Ducatus Historiam Pertinentia* [Capasso 1885, 1892]. Additional documentation derives from collections of *regesta*, including the charters of the Monastery of SS. Severino and Sossio [Pilone 1999], of Monastery of San Gregorio [Pilone 1996; Vetere 2000], and the *Notamento cavato dalli Instrumenti e Privilegii che si conservano nell'Archivio del monasterio di S. Sebastiano di Napoli*², which made it possible to extend the investigation to the end of the twelfth century.

In total, the *corpus* comprises 2,460 items. It is a composite body of documentation characterised by various levels of mediation: nineteenth-century transcriptions, modern *regesta*, and indirect traditions incorporated into later repertories.

2. From Historical Source to Data: Constructing the Analysis

Notarial documents do not provide ready-made lists of properties or places. They record legal acts, and properties appear when they become the object of sale, concession, or donation. The information relevant to this study is therefore embedded within the texts, interwoven with the formal conventions of juridical tradition and the late Latin vocabulary of a society writing around the year 1000.

The basic unit of analysis was not the document as a whole. In this study, an “element of interest” refers to each individual property or spatial unit mentioned in a legal act that becomes the object of juridical action.

A single act may describe multiple properties – land parcels, buildings, cultivated plots, or urban spaces – each treated as an autonomous unit. This analytical “disaggregation” makes it possible to observe more precisely how properties are described and which features recur in the documentation, thereby allowing a closer examination of how different properties are qualified.

To analyse these elements systematically and observe their characteristics at scale, it was necessary to intervene in their form – namely in their structural organisation.

¹ <https://www.iststudiatell.org/fonti.htm>

Acknowledgements: The datasets, code, and maps produced in the course of this research will be made publicly available and progressively updated on the author’s GitHub profile (<https://github.com/xpi-an>), in accordance with FAIR principles. The present study represents a first stage in the systematisation of the data emerging from the analysis and is conceived as a basis for further investigation. For reasons of space, and in order to devote adequate space to the application of digital tools, only some of the most significant elements identified in the course of the analysis have been discussed here. The expansion of the corpus and the integration of additional data with those already included will make it possible to refine the reconstructed framework further.

² BSNSP, ms. XXVIII C 9, cc. 245 – 652.

The *corpus* was structured in tabular format with normalised fields recording: the type of properties, the juridical action affecting it, its location, the documentary source from which the information was extracted, and its chronological context.

The database was organised into three distinct tables: one dedicated to the charters, containing metadata and chronological information; one dedicated to the elements of interest identified within the acts; and one dedicated to places, including their spatial attributes. This structure separates different informational levels – document and chronology, properties, geographical context – reducing redundancy where possible and making the relationships between levels more explicit. The tables were handled in a Python environment using *Pandas* library for data manipulation, *GeoPandas* for spatial data management, and *NetworkX* and *PyVis* for network analysis and visualisation, and were subsequently linked through shared keys. This approach made it possible to recombine the data according to different research questions.

The transition from text to data required explicit methodological choices to render the source into a structured and formalised representation [Schöch 2013]. Terminological variants (e.g. *terra*, *fundus*, *fundicello*, *clausuria*) were normalised and grouped into coherent categories; chronological references were standardised; and topographical information was harmonised as far as possible. This process aims to make the source systematically interrogable while preserving its complexity. The resulting elements were organised into a taxonomy derived from documentary recurrence. The purpose is not to reconstruct a complete image of the territory, but rather to recover what the documentation makes visible. The territory that emerges from the analysis therefore corresponds primarily to the space recorded within documentary practices – that is the space that becomes relevant when it enters juridical transactions.

This selectivity constitutes a meaningful perspective. The properties recorded in the deeds represent an “acted-upon” space, shaped and transformed by communities, and are those over which rights are exercised, relationships negotiated, and material and economic structures organised. Through them, it becomes possible to trace how a community used and structured its territory over time.

Bringing together spatial and temporal dimensions allows patterns of recurrence, regional variation, and change over time to be identified. Computational tools supported historical judgment, allowing us to work on a large dataset while keeping classificatory decisions transparent and translating these relationships into graphs and thematic maps. These visualisations are more than an illustrative device: by making concentrations, imbalances, and dynamics immediately perceptible – phenomena that would be difficult to detect through sequential reading alone – they form an integral part of the interpretative process [Dunn 2019] and allow for large-scale comparative observation across the documentary record [Moretti 2000; Birkholz and Budke 2021]. This interpretative use of network

and spatial modelling aligns with recent applications in digital humanities, where relational visualisation functions as a heuristic tool rather than mere illustration [Gabay & Vitali 2019; Smail 2025].

Distributions, Concentrations, Dynamics

FIG. 1: Spatial distribution of documented elements of interest across the Neapolitan territory (9th –12th centuries). Regional clusters (*Ager Neapolitanus*, *Plagiense*, *Liburia*, Naples, and others) display the quantitative concentration of occurrences, while the pop-up illustrates the structured metadata associated with each record (location, typology, juridical action, and date).

The initial stage of analysis examined the distribution of relevant occurrences within the documentation across the different regions of the Neapolitan territory. The aim was to identify where, and with what intensity, notarial records register and formalise properties, places, and resources. Their concentration thus makes it possible to pinpoint the areas in which space most frequently enters the documentary record.

The overall distribution reveals a clear predominance of the *Ager Neapolitanus* (39% of the total) and the *Plagiense* (18%), which together account for the largest share of attestations. They are followed, at significantly lower levels, by Naples (17%), the *Liburia* (10%), and the more peripheral zones. The resulting picture is that of a strongly polarised system, in which the areas most immediately connected to the city occupy a central position within the documentary dynamics.

This territorial concentration becomes even more meaningful when examined over the medium to long term. The chronological trend, divided into twenty-year intervals, shows a gradual increase in

occurrences between the mid-tenth century and the early decades of the eleventh, with a peak between 1000 and 1039. This phase is followed by a marked contraction in the subsequent twenty-year period, particularly evident in the *Ager Neapolitanus* and the *Plagiense*.

FIG. 2: Chronological trend of documented occurrences by region, divided into twenty-year intervals (900–1199). The graph highlights the predominance of the *Ager Neapolitanus* and the *Plagiense*, the peak between 1000–1039, and the subsequent contraction, followed by renewed growth in the late eleventh and twelfth centuries.

Although the data indicate a common general trend, they also reveal local variations. The attestations relating to the city of Naples do not exhibit an equally pronounced decline: despite fluctuations, the presence of urban properties in contractual records maintains a certain continuity. The contraction primarily affects rural and peri-urban landed interests, whereas the formalisation of urban space appears to be less significantly impacted by this phase of slowdown.

From the late eleventh century onwards, a new phase of growth becomes visible, which took on substantial dimensions in the twelfth century. Again, the revival was mainly concentrated in the areas closest to the urban centre, where the eastern suburban zone between *Porta Nobense* and the present-day Piazza Mercato assumes increasing importance. More peripheral zones, by contrast, continue to be characterised by discontinuous and quantitatively limited documentary presence.

The overall pattern thus suggests a selective dynamic: during phases of contraction, interest in more distant areas diminishes most sharply; during phases of expansion, growth primarily affects those areas most closely integrated into the urban system. The evidence does not allow for a direct reconstruction of the region's overall economic trajectory. Instead, the analysis highlights the territorial configurations that become visible within the documentary record and allows us to identify the areas most intensively involved in regulated economic activity.

It does, however, make it possible to identify the areas most intensively involved in regulated economic activity and to reconstruct the forms through which such dynamics were organised: the

recurrence of lease concessions, the variety of contractual arrangements, the distribution of cultivations, and the changes over time in both the value and management of properties.

3.2 Complexity and Articulation of the Documented Landscape

While the geographical distribution of the elements of interest shows where the documentation concentrates its attention, the analysis of landscape attestations makes it possible to observe how those places are qualified and defined as “agricultural spaces” [Toubert 1993, 93], i.e. as productive units characterised by specific cultivations, internal articulations, and recognisable forms of exploitation. However, not all elements of interest provide the same level of detail: in some cases, land is indicated in generic terms; in others, it is accompanied by the specification of crops, by the presence of multiple productive types, or by more complex internal structuring. The distinction between simple occurrences and landscape co-occurrences makes it possible to capture this difference. An occurrence refers here to the presence of a single cultivation category associated with a property; a co-occurrence designates the presence within the same element of interest of multiple landscape categories.

Land where multiple categories appear (e.g. vines and cereals, or vines, olive trees and legumes together) suggests a composite use of agricultural space and greater descriptive attention in the formalisation of the deed. This is not just an agronomic issue: it is also a factor that affects how the property is defined juridically.

FIG. 3: Landscape variety by region and twenty-year interval. Heatmap representing the number of distinct cultivation categories recorded within each area over time, showing increased descriptive complexity in the Ager Neapolitanus and Plagiense during phases of documentary expansion.

The diachronic analysis shows that landscape complexity changes over time. Between the mid-tenth century and the early decades of the eleventh century, the number of distinct categories recorded within each area increases, with a particular concentration in the *Ager Neapolitanus* and the *Plagiense*.

In these zones, not only does the number of attestations rise, but the internal variety of descriptions also becomes more pronounced.

The contraction observed in the period 1040-1059, in line with the decline highlighted in Figure 2, manifests itself not only as a quantitative decrease but also as a reduction in descriptive variety, especially in areas less integrated into the urban system. By contrast, from the late eleventh century onwards, and more clearly in the twelfth, complexity begins to increase again, once more concentrating in the zones closest to the city.

The greater descriptive complexity recorded in the areas most directly connected to the city does not merely reflect a different mode of representing the territory; it also provides concrete evidence for assessing forms of land use. In these contexts, the documentation does not merely refer to land in generic terms but specifies its cultivations, internal articulations, and at times, its modes of management, thereby making it possible to observe the productive structure of individual landed units.

The higher documentary density recorded in the *Ager Neapolitanus* and the *Plagiense* not only allows for the quantification of attestations, but also enables a detailed examination of the structure of agricultural landscapes. The size of the sample, in fact, enables a more precise distinction between cultivation types and allows their development over time to be traced.

FIG. 4: Distribution and diachronic development of cultivation categories. (A, C) Overall percentage distribution of landscape categories in the Ager Neapolitanus and Plagiense. (B, D) Twenty-year trends of principal cultivations (cereals, vines, olives, legumes), illustrating differing productive configurations and internal articulation between the two areas.

The overall distribution of categories (Fig. 4 A–C) reveals significant differences. In the *Ager Neapolitanus*, cereals and vines each account for about a quarter of the attestations, while olives appear marginal; the resulting picture is that of an area strongly oriented towards cereal and viticultural production. In the *Plagiense*, by contrast, the relative weight of olives increases markedly, and the cereal component appears less dominant. Two distinct productive configurations emerge, both integrated into the urban system, yet not overlapping.

If one examines the twenty-year trends (Fig. 4 B–D), the distinction becomes even more pronounced. In the *Ager Neapolitanus*, the presence of vines assumes an increasingly prominent role between the late 10th and the eleventh century. In the *Plagiense*, by contrast, the fluctuation between cereals, vines, and olives suggests a more internally articulated structure, with no clear phase in which one crop prevails over the others.

The comparison between the two areas acquires further significance when considering the different numbers of items of interest recorded in each. Despite this marked quantitative disparity, the relative incidence of references to the principal cultivations suggests that, in the *Plagiense*, cultivation-related attestations occupy a proportionally larger share of the total recorded elements. The resulting picture is that of an area in which documentary attention is more consistently focused on the agricultural dimension, outlining a productive profile even more clearly defined than that of the *Ager Neapolitanus*.

An examination of the internal distribution of cultivations in the two territories across the chronological span considered (Fig. A–D) further shows that the attestations rarely describe rigidly specialised landed units. More often, lands appear in combination with different cultivations or within articulated productive contexts. This feature, within the limits of notarial documentation, suggests an agrarian structure characterised by a degree of internal diversification, particularly in areas closest to the urban core.

4. The case of the Monastery of San Sebastiano

Whereas the previous sections have highlighted distributions and dynamics on a large territorial scale, the analysis of the properties registered for the monastery of San Sebastiano allows us to narrow the field down to a single institutional actor – an urban agent – and examine how a monastic institution positioned itself within the Neapolitan landholding system between the 10th and twelfth centuries.

The case of the monastery of San Sebastiano was reconstructed by selecting those acts in which the institution appears as the agent of the juridical action, from within the entire corpus analysed. This

subset allows to observe closely how a monastic institution fitted into the documented space and into the economic and productive practices of the territories.

FIG. 5 Cluster map of properties attributable to the monastery of San Sebastiano. Points aggregated by proximity represent documented properties; colours distinguish juridical actions (donations, rents, acquisitions, others), and cluster size reflects concentration. The map visualises the territorial projection of the monastic patrimony.

The cluster map (Fig. 5) makes it possible to visualise three informational levels simultaneously: the territorial location of the properties, their quantitative concentration within each area, and the juridical category through which they appear in the acts (acquisitions, leases, donations, and other forms).

Points are aggregated by proximity; in the interactive version, expanding the clusters reveals the details of individual attestations. The colour of the points distinguishes juridical actions, while the size of each cluster reflects the density of occurrences. The image therefore represents not merely a geographical distribution but a broader synthesis of the documented presence of the institution across different territorial contexts.

The map of properties attributable to the monastery shows a widespread presence extending even into more peripheral areas such as the *Cimitirensis* territory. Although the institution maintains an urban

centre of gravity, its landed expansion follows diversified trajectories and extends beyond the limits of immediate proximity.

The clusters are distributed along productive areas already identified as central in the broader analysis and are largely linked to the principal mechanism through which the monastery's patrimony expanded: donations. The spatial distribution of properties thus reflects a logic of landed concentration which, grafting itself onto an already structured economic fabric, simultaneously contributed to its further definition and consolidation.

In this sense, the case of San Sebastiano highlights the functioning of the metropolitan system outlined in the preceding sections at an institutional scale: a configuration in which the city operates as a centre for the collection, management, and redistribution of resources originating from the surrounding areas.

FIG. 6: Network graph of juridical relationships involving the monastery of San Sebastiano. The monastery constitutes the central node, connected to places where its properties are recorded. Edge colour and thickness correspond to juridical categories and frequency, highlighting patterns of concentration and patrimonial management strategies.

The network graph offers a second mode of interpretation. Here, the monastery constitutes the central node, connected to the various places in which properties attributable to it appear. The thickness and colour of the edges correspond to the type of juridical action, making it possible to distinguish visually the different ways in which the institution operated across territories.

The network configuration renders explicit what remains implicit in the map: these are not merely holdings, but juridical relationships reiterated within specific territorial contexts. Some nodes are connected by multiple edges, indicating a higher frequency of operations; others appear as more isolated connections. The case of San Sebastiano thus concretely demonstrates the potential of structured analysis to make visible territorial and relational configurations that, in the sequential reading of individual acts, remain fragmented or obscured.

The network highlights the prominence of rental contracts and of deals implying the productive exploitation of properties, suggesting a form of management oriented towards the active valorisation of the patrimony. Distinct trajectories of landed investment become visible, alongside repeated concentration in specific areas – once again, the *Ager Neapolitanus* and the *Plagiense* emerge as principal nodes – and a predominance of rental concessions and income-generating arrangements that point to a strategy of patrimonial enhancement rather than mere passive accumulation. In support of this interpretation, it may be noted that of the acquisitions requiring a direct financial outlay by the monastery (22 in total) [Capasso 1885, reg. 47, 140; Libertini 2011, regg. 19, 20, 58, 65, 76, 83, 114, 121, 123, 177, 182, 201, 220, 252, 266, 401], twelve concern lands and estates in the *Ager Neapolitanus* and eight in the *Plagiense*.

Conclusions

The analytical trajectory outlined here makes it possible to reconstruct the territorial configuration that emerges from the notarial documentation between the 10th and twelfth centuries, highlighting a marked polarisation between areas more closely integrated into the urban system and those situated at its periphery. The concentration of attestations in the *Ager Neapolitanus* and in the *Plagiense*, contrasted with the weaker incidence of border areas, suggests new considerations regarding the extent of the space more directly integrated into the urban system. On the basis of the toponyms and micro-toponyms attested in the documentation, and of their approximate georeferencing onto present-day locations, it is possible to suggest, albeit cautiously, an estimated area of 600 km². This reassessment, in relation to estimates proposed elsewhere [Arthur 2002, 82], remains interpretative and should be understood as a working hypothesis rather than a definitive measure of urban control and derives from the specific character of marginal zones such as the *Liburia*, which appear as osmotic borders, spaces of interaction and exchange characterised by a lower degree of urban penetration and exploitation when compared to other regions.

Chronological fluctuations and the varying descriptive articulation of properties show that the documentation does not record the territory in a neutral or uniform manner; rather, it concentrates attention on spaces in which rights, exchanges, and forms of productive organisation intensify. In this

sense, the analysis has not treated the charter as a single testimonial unit, but has instead foregrounded what it describes: properties, cultivations, structures, and modes of exploitation. This approach makes it possible to preserve the internal complexity of the attestations – often multiple within a single act – thus avoiding quantitative simplification and contributing to a fuller picture of the dynamics outlined in recent studies on the economy and society of the Duchy, which have emphasised the increasing articulation of agrarian and landed processes [Feniello 2008; 2011].

The observation of cultivation co-occurrences and their variation over time has further revealed different levels of internal complexity. While the vine had already been identified as the predominant cultivation [Melis 1984; Martin 2006, 20–21; Feniello 2007, 7–11], the analysis has made it possible to quantify its attestations more precisely. More importantly, it has allowed for an assessment of the actual extent of olive cultivation, whose relative scarcity has repeatedly been emphasised [Martin 2006, 6; Feniello 2007, 10–11]. This absence appears more surprising when one considers that oil becomes a recurrent element in rent payments over the course of the twelfth century, particularly in its second half [Libertini 2011, reg. 535; Pilone 1991, regg. 19, 21, 23, 24, 49, 51, 63, 82, 484, 535, 1345, 1524, 1552, 1559].

The case of the monastery of San Sebastiano has confirmed the coherence of these trajectories, showing how the landed projection of an urban actor is inscribed within the same areas already identified as central in the broader analysis. The graphs also show a significant increase in donations from the second half of the eleventh century onwards, a development that can be situated within the wider process of patrimonial accumulation and landed concentration involving Neapolitan ecclesiastical institutions, contributing to the progressive consolidation of more stable and territorially coherent patrimonies [Feniello 2007, 225–226].

More broadly, the work presented here demonstrates the potential of reorganising large documentary corpora through digital methods. The use of computational tools has made it possible to aggregate, filter, and visualise information dispersed across hundreds of acts, allowing concentrations, rhythms, and imbalances within the documentation to become visible at a scale that would be difficult to achieve through sequential reading alone.

The dataset developed here is intended as a structured and verified basis, providing an initial overview of the available documentation, complete with metadata and archival and historical information. By combining historical interpretation with data modelling, it offers a framework that may support additional forms of digital analysis, including automated entity extraction and the development of supervised models for the identification of semantic categories within medieval notarial corpora.

In this sense, the analysis presented does not exhaust the *corpus*'s potential. It establishes an initial interpretative and computational infrastructure, opening new possibilities for the reading and comparison of urban sources.

Archival Sources

BSNSP = Biblioteca della Società Napoletana di Storia Patria, ms. XXVIII C 9, cc. 245 – 652.

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